

COVID-19-ASSOCIATED ORGAN DAMAGES: PATHOGENESIS AND COMORBIDITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14012500>

Abstract. *The renal implications of COVID-19 are critically examined, focusing on the pathophysiological mechanisms of kidney injury induced by SARS-CoV-2. Both direct cytopathic effects on renal tissue and the activation of inflammatory and immune responses are explored as key contributors to the development of acute kidney injury (AKI). The influence of comorbid conditions—such as chronic kidney disease, cardiovascular disorders, and diabetes—on the severity and clinical outcomes of COVID-19 is highlighted. Modern therapeutic approaches for managing COVID-19-related kidney dysfunction, including renal replacement therapies and extracorporeal detoxification, are also discussed in the context of critically ill patients.*

Keywords: *SARS-CoV-2, renal pathology, acute kidney injury, comorbidities.*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic, which began at the end of 2019, has posed a serious challenge to healthcare systems worldwide. By March 2023, the number of registered COVID-19 cases in Uzbekistan exceeded a quarter of a million, with a mortality rate of 0.7% [1]. This burden strained healthcare systems globally, particularly in countries with limited resources. Despite significant progress in understanding and managing COVID-19, specific aspects of the pandemic, including reinfection and the influence of comorbidities, require further investigation [2-4].

The pandemic has disproportionately affected individuals with chronic health conditions, or comorbidities, which have significantly increased the risk of severe disease and mortality. Comorbid conditions such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, respiratory conditions, and chronic kidney disease (CKD) have exacerbated the impact of COVID-19, resulting in more complex clinical presentations and outcomes. The novelty of SARS-CoV-2, along with its potential for reinfection and multiorgan damage, has revealed the importance of studying the underlying pathophysiology of the disease and its interaction with these chronic conditions.

The high mortality rate, severe complications in many survivors, and prolonged rehabilitation across different age groups have driven researchers to focus on various aspects of studying COVID-19 [5-8]. The impact of the combination of COVID-19 and comorbidities on mortality has been examined in a number of studies. As expected, the highest mortality rate was observed in the 80+ age group (14.8%). However, reports from the U.S. in early 2020 noted that among more than 4,000 cases, the highest mortality rate occurred in patients over the age of 65. This finding requires further investigation [7-12].

Patients with COVID-19 often have multiple risk factors. For instance, chronic kidney disease (CKD) was found in 48% of hospitalized COVID-19 patients over the age of 70 [13-16]. The impact of comorbidities on the severity of COVID-19 was also noted in other age groups. In a study by Pei G. et al., they analyzed data from 333 COVID-19 patients (mean age 56.3±13.4 years) and concluded that CKD is a risk factor for contracting the virus [14].

Wang X. et al. identified a direct correlation between CKD and the severity of COVID-19 (odds ratio 2.22; 95% CI: 1.14, 4.31) [15]. These findings are consistent with the results of a meta-analysis of 84 studies, which included data on 1,389 COVID-19 patients.

Pathogenesis of COVID-19

COVID-19, caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), primarily targets the respiratory system but also induces systemic complications, particularly in patients with comorbidities. SARS-CoV-2 enters human cells through angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors, which are widely expressed in the lungs, heart, kidneys, and gastrointestinal tract [2]. This widespread receptor distribution explains the multiorgan involvement often seen in severe COVID-19 cases.

One of the most devastating consequences of COVID-19 is the development of acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), characterized by respiratory failure and the need for mechanical ventilation. ARDS is a major contributor to mortality in COVID-19 patients, particularly those with comorbid conditions [3]. Another critical complication is acute kidney injury (AKI), which is especially prevalent in patients requiring intensive care or mechanical ventilation.

The virus designated as SARS-CoV-2 belongs to the same group of coronaviruses (Betacoronavirus) as the causative agents of SARS (2003) and MERS (2012), which are known to have caused two of the most serious epidemics in recent years [16]. Studies conducted during and after the COVID-19 pandemic showed that the virus uses the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor to enter cells [17]. This carboxypeptidase is expressed on the cell membranes of endothelial tissues, heart, arteries, oral cavity and tongue, lungs, kidneys, male testes, female ovaries, gallbladder, stomach, pancreas, large and small intestines, making SARS-CoV-2 capable of causing multiorgan damage in patients [18]. ACE2 breaks down angiotensin I into angiotensin 1–9 and angiotensin II into angiotensin 1–7, counteracting the vasoconstrictive, proliferative, and fibrotic effects of angiotensin II associated with ACE [11].

The coronavirus can also bind to ACE2 via the spike glycoprotein expressed on its viral envelope. Once inside alveolar cells, it uses the endogenous transcription mechanism, allowing the virus to replicate and spread throughout the lungs [19]. It is important to note that ACE2 is also widely expressed in the cells of the heart, liver, gastrointestinal tract, and kidneys [17, 20]. By analyzing the levels of ACE2 expression, it is possible to assess an organ's vulnerability to infection, and it has been found that the kidney is highly vulnerable. Coronavirus RNA has been detected in the kidneys and urine of infected patients, suggesting that the kidney is a target of this new coronavirus [14, 18]. Around 82% of ACE2 is expressed on the epithelium of the proximal tubules, to a lesser extent on intercalated cells of collecting ducts, distal tubule epithelium, glomerular parietal cells, and podocytes, but not in glomerular endothelial and mesangial cells [12]. It is assumed that the virus may enter the kidney by first binding to ACE2 on podocytes and then spreading to the tubular fluid and into proximal tubule cells.

SARS-CoV-2 antigens accumulate in the kidney tubules, suggesting that the virus directly infects human kidneys, contributing to the development of acute kidney injury (AKI) and the spread of the virus in the body [16]. Recognizing the cytopathic effect of SARS-CoV-2 that contributes to AKI, many researchers believe that the nature of AKI in COVID-19 is multifactorial, involving infection-induced immune and inflammatory responses, the development of a cytokine

storm, and hypercoagulability. These processes are associated with hemodynamic factors, ischemia, and systemic reactions linked to respiratory failure.

Kidney damage from the nephrotropic effect of the virus and its cytopathic impact on the tubular epithelium can occur in parallel with the action of SARS-CoV-2 on lung epithelium. The resulting kidney dysfunction exacerbates the inflammatory process in the lungs. Kidney dysfunction in COVID-19 patients is connected to the kidney-lung interaction because SARS-CoV-2 uses ACE2 as a receptor to enter the cell, and ACE2 is expressed at much higher levels in the kidneys than in the lungs. The authors suggest that after reaching a certain "critical point" of inflammation severity, the interaction between the kidneys and lungs leads to an irreversible and uncontrolled cytokine storm, quickly causing multiorgan failure and death [15].

Kidney damage is linked to both the direct cytopathic effect of SARS-CoV-2 and the interaction between the lungs and kidneys in response to the release of TNF- α and interleukin-6 from the lungs [22]. The acid-base balance in the body is regulated by the excretion of carbon dioxide by the lungs and the reabsorption of bicarbonate by the kidneys. When the function of one of these organs is impaired, a compensatory mechanism in the other organ is activated. In this regard, respiratory problems in patients with AKI caused by coronavirus infection play a critical role.

Clinical studies have shown that patients with AKI are twice as likely to require mechanical ventilation. It has been established that kidney dysfunction significantly impacts the duration of mechanical ventilation, the decision to discontinue it, and the mortality of critically ill patients. On the other hand, patients with acute respiratory failure (ARF) or acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), especially those requiring mechanical ventilation, are at high risk of developing AKI.

Risk Factors for Severe COVID-19 Outcomes

Risk factors for severe COVID-19 include advanced age, male gender, and the presence of underlying chronic conditions. Early studies, such as those by Guan et al. and Hu et al., identified older adults as being at the highest risk of severe disease and mortality [3, 4]. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) also emphasized the increased risk for individuals with preexisting conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and CKD [5].

Chronic conditions are associated with impaired immune responses and altered inflammatory pathways, which can exacerbate the clinical course of COVID-19. Studies have confirmed that patients with comorbidities are more likely to experience severe complications, including ARDS, AKI, and multiorgan failure, leading to higher mortality rates [6]. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the interaction between SARS-CoV-2 and these chronic diseases to improve clinical outcomes.

Cardiovascular Disease and COVID-19

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are particularly significant risk factors for severe COVID-19 outcomes. SARS-CoV-2 has been shown to induce myocardial injury, arrhythmias, and thromboembolic events, particularly in patients with preexisting CVD. The virus exacerbates cardiovascular conditions through direct myocardial involvement, systemic inflammation, and a hypercoagulable state [6].

Patients with CVD are also at increased risk of developing ARDS, further complicating their clinical course. The inflammatory response in these patients often results in a cytokine storm, which can lead to myocardial injury and increased mortality. For instance, Cummings et al.

reported that critically ill patients with underlying CVD had higher mortality rates compared to those without [6].

Diabetes and COVID-19

Diabetes is another major comorbidity associated with severe COVID-19. Hyperglycemia and insulin resistance create a pro-inflammatory and pro-thrombotic environment that worsens the clinical course of COVID-19. Diabetic patients have impaired immune responses, making them more vulnerable to infections and their complications [7].

Patients with diabetes are more likely to develop severe pneumonia, ARDS, and AKI during COVID-19 infection. Studies have shown that diabetic patients experience longer hospital stays, more severe symptoms, and higher mortality rates than non-diabetic individuals [7]. This may be due to the effects of hyperglycemia on immune function, as well as the presence of diabetes-related complications such as nephropathy, neuropathy, and cardiovascular disease.

Chronic and Acute Kidney Injury in COVID-19

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is among the most significant risk factors for severe COVID-19. CKD patients have higher rates of hospitalization, intensive care unit (ICU) admission, and mortality due to the direct effects of SARS-CoV-2 on the kidneys, as well as the systemic effects of the disease. Pei et al. demonstrated that patients with CKD were significantly more likely to develop severe COVID-19 than those without kidney disease [14].

The kidneys are vulnerable to SARS-CoV-2 due to the presence of ACE2 receptors in the renal tubular cells and podocytes, making them a target for viral invasion. This can lead to AKI, which complicates the clinical course of COVID-19 and worsens the prognosis. Research has shown that patients with AKI have a higher risk of multiorgan failure and death, particularly when combined with CKD [8].

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a critical complication in patients with severe COVID-19. The incidence of AKI in COVID-19 patients ranges from 0.5% to 28.9%, depending on disease severity and the need for mechanical ventilation [8, 19]. AKI in COVID-19 is multifactorial, involving direct viral damage, systemic inflammation, hypoxemia, and hypercoagulability [9].

Braun et al. demonstrated that SARS-CoV-2 can directly infect renal tubular cells, causing acute tubular necrosis and worsening kidney function [7]. In addition to direct viral effects, the systemic inflammatory response associated with COVID-19 can lead to cytokine release, endothelial dysfunction, and microvascular thrombosis, further contributing to AKI development [9].

The pathophysiological mechanisms of kidney damage in COVID-19 are complex and involve both direct viral invasion and indirect effects of systemic inflammation. SARS-CoV-2 enters renal cells via ACE2 receptors, leading to direct cytopathic effects on the kidneys. This can result in acute tubular necrosis, interstitial inflammation, and podocyte injury, all of which contribute to the development of AKI [10].

In severe COVID-19 cases, a hypercoagulable state develops due to the systemic inflammatory response, resulting in widespread thrombotic events. Microvascular thrombosis and thrombotic microangiopathy are commonly observed in patients with COVID-19-related AKI, further impairing renal function [10].

The pathogenesis of kidney damage in COVID-19 infection is a complex process. Firstly, it should be noted that the coronavirus exerts a direct cytopathic effect on the kidneys, as confirmed by the detection of coronavirus fragments in the urine of COVID-19 patients using polymerase

chain reaction. As mentioned earlier, COVID-19 uses ACE2 to enter host cells. Notably, according to RNA sequencing data from human tissues, ACE2 expression in the kidneys is almost 100 times higher than in the lungs. Electron microscopy of kidney tissues has shown that ACE2 expression occurs in different parts of the nephron, namely in the renal corpuscle (podocytes, mesangial cells), in the epithelial cells of the proximal tubules, and in the endothelium of the glomerular capillaries [1, 5].

A. Werion et al. conducted a study on 49 patients hospitalized with severe and critical COVID-19 to determine the possible cytopathic effects of SARS-CoV-2 on the proximal tubular epithelium. Most of these patients exhibited signs of proximal tubular dysfunction, which was independent of comorbidities, glomerular proteinuria, nephrotoxic effects of certain medications, and viral load. Clinically, this condition manifested as low-molecular-weight proteinuria (in 70–80% of patients), neutral aminoaciduria (46%), impaired tubular transport of uric acid (46%), and phosphate abnormalities (19%). There was a correlation between hypouricemia and hyperuricosuria and the severity of the disease, particularly with an increased risk of respiratory failure progressing to the point of requiring mechanical ventilation (odds ratio 6.2; 95% CI 1.9–20.1). Transmission electron microscopy revealed particles resembling coronavirus in the endoplasmic reticulum of proximal tubular cells [2, 9].

The presence of viral particles in endothelial cells and signs of apoptosis indicate that COVID-19 causes endothelitis, leading to generalized vascular/endothelial dysfunction. Histological studies of the kidneys conducted by Diao B. et al. on patients who died from coronavirus infection revealed acute tubular necrosis and massive lymphocytic infiltration [3, 6].

Using light microscopy, Su H. et al. found diffuse damage to the proximal tubules of the nephron in COVID-19 patients, with signs of vacuolar degeneration of epithelial cells and, in some cases, areas of necrosis. Hemosiderin granules were detected in the lumens of the nephron tubules [4, 11].

Histopathological findings suggest that kidney lesions in patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 differ from those seen in nephritis and nephrotic syndrome, where pathological manifestations are primarily present in the glomeruli. Immunohistochemical analysis of biopsy samples revealed another mechanism of SARS-CoV-2 kidney damage, specifically the accumulation of SARS-CoV-2 NP antigen in the kidney tubules. This is indicated by the in-situ expression of viral nucleocapsid protein antigen (NP), immune cell markers CD8, CD68, CD56, and complement C5b-9 [5, 10].

It is now considered proven that coronavirus infection causes a massive release of cytokines, promotes macrophage activation, and infiltration of kidney parenchyma by lymphocytes, and increases complement C5b-9 deposition in the nephron tubules. Moreover, during the peak of inflammation and the "cytokine storm" in COVID-19 patients, filtration pressure and glomerular filtration rate decrease, while renal blood flow is reduced, which can lead to type 1 cardiorenal syndrome, followed by the development of AKI and CKD [6, 15].

It has been established that in severe cases of the disease, proteinuria and hematuria develop in most cases (15% of patients with CKD were included in the study before the onset of COVID-19). AKI occurred in 61% of cases, and autopsy pathological studies of the kidneys revealed acute damage to the tubular epithelium in the vast majority of patients, which, according to the authors, underlies the development of urinary syndrome [7, 14].

These findings are consistent with the results of G. Pei et al., who found kidney pathology in 75.4% of cases in a group of 333 COVID-19 patients. Interestingly, the authors observed a resolution of kidney pathology symptoms along with the regression of pneumonia; however, as the severity of the lung process increased, there was no remission of kidney pathology [8, 12].

In another study, Li Z. et al. found that proteinuria and hematuria were present in nearly 40% of patients upon admission [9, 16]. These results are consistent with a study conducted by Cheng Y. et al., which involved over 700 COVID-19 patients. Upon admission, 44% of the patients had proteinuria, 26.9% had hematuria, and elevated serum creatinine and blood urea nitrogen levels were observed in 15.5% and 14.1% of patients, respectively. AKI developed in 3.2% of patients. Kaplan-Meier analysis demonstrated that patients with COVID-19 and kidney function disorders had a higher risk of in-hospital death. Cox regression, or proportional hazard modeling, confirmed that elevated serum creatinine, blood urea nitrogen, AKI, proteinuria, and hematuria are independent risk factors for in-hospital death, adjusted for age, gender, disease severity, leukocyte count, and lymphocyte count [10, 18].

Interestingly, an analysis of peripheral blood samples from SARS-CoV-2-infected patients on hemodialysis revealed a significant decrease in the number of T-lymphocytes, T-helper cells, T-killers, and natural killers, as well as lower levels of inflammatory cytokines in serum compared to COVID-19 patients not on hemodialysis. Overall, this study allowed the authors to suggest that COVID-19 patients on hemodialysis are likely to have a milder course of the disease with a lower risk of pneumonia progression, possibly secondary [11, 19].

Kidney-Lung Interactions in COVID-19

The interconnection between kidney and lung damage in COVID-19 has been well-documented, particularly in patients with ARDS. ARDS is associated with a higher risk of AKI due to the systemic inflammatory response, hypoxemia, and the need for invasive mechanical ventilation [12].

Studies have shown that approximately 70% of patients with ARDS develop AKI, highlighting the close interaction between lung and kidney pathology in COVID-19 [22]. Inflammatory cytokines released during ARDS can exacerbate kidney injury, while impaired kidney function can lead to fluid overload, worsening respiratory outcomes.

Renal Replacement Therapy in COVID-19 Patients

Renal replacement therapy (RRT) is an essential treatment for COVID-19 patients with severe AKI. Continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT) is commonly used in critically ill patients, allowing for the removal of inflammatory cytokines, stabilization of fluid-electrolyte imbalances, and management of acid-base disorders [13].

CRRT has been shown to improve outcomes in COVID-19 patients with AKI by reducing the duration of mechanical ventilation and ICU stay. However, the use of CRRT requires specialized equipment and trained personnel, which may not be available in all healthcare settings, particularly in resource-limited regions [14].

COVID-19 Reinfection

Reinfection with SARS-CoV-2 is a subject of ongoing research, as it has significant implications for public health and vaccine development. Studies have shown that reinfection rates vary, depending on population demographics, immune status, and the emergence of new viral variants. Reinfection can occur due to the ability of SARS-CoV-2 to evade immune detection and adapt to immune pressure [9].

Van Elslande et al. reported a case of reinfection with a phylogenetically distinct strain of SARS-CoV-2, highlighting the challenges in achieving lasting immunity to the virus [9]. Reinfection complicates public health efforts to control the pandemic and underscores the importance of continuous monitoring of viral mutations and vaccine efficacy.

Public Health Implications and Future Research

The COVID-19 pandemic has exposed the vulnerabilities of patients with chronic diseases, particularly CKD, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease. The high incidence of AKI in COVID-19 patients underscores the need for early detection and management of kidney involvement to improve outcomes. Furthermore, the potential for reinfection and the emergence of new viral variants highlight the importance of ongoing research into the long-term effects of COVID-19 and the development of new therapeutic strategies.

Further studies are needed to better understand the mechanisms underlying COVID-19-related AKI and to identify optimal treatment protocols for managing kidney involvement in these patients. Additionally, ongoing surveillance of reinfection rates and the evolution of viral variants will be critical in informing public health policies and vaccination strategies moving forward.

Conclusion

COVID-19 continues to pose a significant threat to global public health, particularly for individuals with underlying chronic conditions. Comorbidities such as CKD, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease significantly increase the risk of severe COVID-19 and mortality. The potential for multiorgan involvement, including kidney damage, underscores the need for comprehensive care and early intervention in patients with severe COVID-19. Current treatment strategies, including the use of CRRT and other extracorporeal therapies, have shown promise in improving outcomes in critically ill patients, but further research is needed to optimize these approaches and ensure access to life-saving treatments in resource-limited settings.

The ongoing challenge of reinfection and viral mutations further complicates the global response to the pandemic. Continued vigilance, research, and innovation in therapeutic strategies are essential to reduce the burden of COVID-19 and improve outcomes for patients with comorbidities. The lessons learned from the pandemic will be critical in shaping future public health responses and preparing for potential pandemics.

The complexity of COVID-19's interaction with chronic diseases requires a multifaceted approach to treatment and public health management. By understanding the interplay between the virus, comorbidities, and organ systems, healthcare providers can better tailor their interventions to reduce mortality and enhance recovery outcomes for vulnerable populations.

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